

THE PRAGMATIC AND LINGUOCULTURAL PECULIARITIES OF BRITISH AND AMERICAN WRITTEN COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: the article deals with the differences between the American and the British variants of the English language at the lexical and semantic level. The author reveals two main types of oppositions: lexical and semantic divergences and lexical and semantic analogues. These main types of oppositions are analyzed. The author finds out correlation between divergent and general elements, establishes the reasons for the occurrence of these differences and defines their place both in the system of one of the variants and in the system of the literary language as a whole. Within the framework of lexical and semantic divergences and analogues the author reveals one-sidedly and two-sidedly locally marked oppositions.

Keywords: the American variant of the English language, the British variant of the English language, comparative and contrastive analysis, lexical and semantic level, lexical and semantic analogues, lexical and semantic divergence.

Introduction: Revitalization of American English will reach the level of international communication and the consequent increase in the requirements for the communicative competence of a business person focus on changing the approach to teaching English in high schools. In this connection the question arises about the inclusion of comparative analysis of the US (AE - American English) and the British (BE - British English) versions of the English language in general English language training system.

It should be noted that American English is significantly different from national standard. In this case, the differences relate to all of its aspects: spelling, grammar, vocabulary and phonetics. In contact with the American English language practice, students are faced with the problem of lack of understanding of information due to the existing differences between the languages they are learning in the classroom.

That is why linguists are increasingly raising the issue of the introduction of compulsory teaching American English in the foreign languages department universities [1]. And because more differences between the two main variants of the English language are detected at the lexical level, at training American English emphasis should be given to the formation of lexical skill.

II. Materials and methods As a material for this study, the issue of The British and American media. In the course of the paper the following research methods were used: structural analysis, contextual analysis, discursive analysis.

III. About the concept of lexical units in linguoculturology on the basis of economic discourse.

Lexical units of BE, included in the standard language, do not show significant regional variations. With the vocabulary of American English is somewhat different. Part of AE vocabulary represented localized versions, i.e. lexical units, the use of which is restricted geographically. However, data obtained as a result of studies conducted by the American linguist Atwood showed that localized variations in speech predominate older and less educated and informants are recessive phenomenon [2].

Competing with the synonymous from the American and general English units, they are clearly inferior to the latter on the frequency of use in the speech of educated people and gradually replaced beyond language. Americanisms, prevalence throughout the United States, covering, in turn, a broad conceptual scope and outnumber geographically limited options many times. As a result, for comparison with Briticisms and general English lexical units we will attract only those words and speech patterns that have no territorial restrictions in AE. Thus, one can imagine the lexical-semantic system of American as a single microsystem, opposing microsystem of the British variant within the framework of macrostandard English.

For example, in the article «Untying the Knot», devoted to the problem of divorce, a block of three interrogative sentences is able to intensify the severity of the problem due to the enhanced presentation of information about its various aspects, namely, the meaning of love and marriage in the lives of people on the causes of divorce: Is it possible to imagine that Ronald loved Patricia or that Donald truly cared for Marla? What does love mean to someone who presents his bride with a prenuptial on the eve of their wedding, stipulating that she would get many millions of dollars for a marriage of four years, but only \$ 1 million for less than that - and then discards her on the deadline? And what does love mean to a woman who'd sign on that particular dotted line? [The New York Times].

We find the following example in the newspaper «The New York Times»:

This appears unstoppable. Two hours between the first shots and second round of carnage and still unstoppable by the authorities. Can anyone see the sense of

the Right to Bear Arms? Unless that means now that everyone HAS to carry a weapon?

In this example, devoted to the consideration of issues to bear arms, rhetorical questions aimed at encouraging readers to express their attitude to the problem of self-defence. Cause the publication of this article in the light began shooting, which was opened on the campus of an American university. Therefore, the rhetorical question posed by the author, not only focus on the expression of indignation over the incident, but also to urge the readers to the joint search for a solution. As shown by further analysis, the use of interrogative sentences is almost unusual for British problematic articles.

This fact can be explained, in our opinion, as following by the British belief in certain ideas, traditions. In contrast to the American authors of problematic articles that are inclined to resort to the formulation of various kinds of questions, thereby demonstrating inquisitive mind and a tendency to seek solutions to problems through the answers to the questions, the authors of the British influence on the audience by means of arguments. For example: Thesis - it has been a terrible few days for the Prime Minister. Arguments - One [Mr Brown's closest ally] said: «It's a bad moment. There will be a hit, but we need to absorb it» [The Telegraph]. Turning to the authoritative opinion, the author refers frequently to a particular person (in this case it tends to emphasize the weight of the quoted specialist and for that indicate the position occupied by them and position), at least - a group of individuals (names is not called, for example, analysts, researchers, etc.).

Thus, in the above example, the statement that the Prime Minister of England has experienced as non-terrible days, during which he was required to cancel the scheduled general selections, confirmed by arguments is a statement a close associate of Mr. Brown that the incident really unpleasant and it will be discussed in the press for a long time. In another example, the argument we find a link to the representative of the Conservative Party, which explains the employment of the majority of new jobs foreigners Migration British policy and the issuance of work visas:

Thesis - 54 per cent of all new jobs in Britain - 862,000 jobs - were taken by foreigners , compared to 731,000 jobs for Britons. Arguments - James Clappison, the Tory MP who obtained the figures, said Britain's place in the table was due to its migration policies and the issuing of work permits [The Telegraph].

GOOD

Meaning in common - "fine, nice" etc. Additional meaning in AmE - "valid" (Trudgill and Hannah, 1997: 90) In the case of the word "good", a different approach had to be applied because the meaning of "valid" proved to be rather marginal. We therefore intentionally located collocates that co-occur with the word "good" in its additional American meaning. In this meaning, the adjective "good" occurs only in predicative position.

The scope was, therefore set to the position 4 -0. The collocations are sorted by relevancy (with the minimum frequency set at 10 -10). Where possible, the side-by-side comparison function was used.

This search provided a convincing proof that in this case, although its occurrence is rather rare, the American additional meaning entered British English. The following example gives evidence of the American use of the word "good" in British English: he was told that his tickets were only good for the front door. In turn, contextually-emotive lexicon environment and Topeka-emotive lexicon in the British and American press are relatively uniform distribution:

[The New York Times] - For many people, the sanctions (Topeka-emotive lexicon) on Iraq were one of the decade's great crimes, . Anger at the United States and Britain, the two principal architects of the policy, often ran white hot. Denis J. Halliday, the United Nations humanitarian coordinator in Iraq for part of the sanctions (Topeka-emotive lexicon) era, expressed :

«We are in the process of destroying (contextually-emotive lexicon environment) an entire society. " [The Guardian]. - In the windswept fenland of rural Cambridgeshire, the government has embarked on a controversial treatment programme (Topeka-emotive lexicon) designed to protect the public from Britain's most dangerous mentally disordered criminals. But many psychiatrists see the scheme (Topeka-emotional vocabulary) as a flawed (contextually-emotional vocabulary environment) political gesture and fear it will turn them from doctors into jailers. As shown by further analysis of the material, in the implementation of a pragmatic exposure to problematic articles there is no small role for metaphors. However, the presence of metaphors is more typical for American problem articles.

Every working adult has known one - a boss who loves making subordinates squirm, whose moods radiate through the office, sending workers scurrying for cover, whose very voice causes stomach muscles to clench and pulses to quicken [The New York Times].

Conclusion: Thus, we can say that there are two kinds of polemical linguocultural discourse - British and American, which find expression in the language level. The impact of data carried varieties of discourse, receives explicit Linguocultural colouring, which will continue to expand the understanding of the mechanisms of the organization and implementation of exposure in the media.

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